

Studies in Outer-Sphere Complexation—Part I : Tris(2-Guanidiniumbenzimidazole)chromium(III) Salts in Aqueous Solutions

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A conductometric study of the equilibrium $\text{Cr}(\text{GBH})_3^{3+} + \text{X}^- \rightleftharpoons \text{Cr}(\text{GBH})_3\text{X}^{2+}$, where GBH=2-guanidinobenzimidazole and $\text{X}^- = \text{Cl}^-$, Br^- , and NO_3^- , has been carried out in aqueous solutions at 25°, 35° and 45°. The association constants (60.8-24.4 l.mole⁻¹) of the outer-sphere complexes, $\text{Cr}(\text{GBH})_3\text{X}^{2+}$, compare well with those of known cobalt(III) systems. Thermodynamic functions, viz, changes in free energy ($-\Delta G^\circ = 2434 - 2019$ cal mole⁻¹), enthalpy ($\Delta H^\circ = 5336 - 3268$ cal mole⁻¹) and entropy ($\Delta S^\circ = 26.07 - 16.63$ cal mole⁻¹ deg⁻¹) have been calculated from the values of equilibrium constants at different temperatures. Ionic radii of $\text{Cr}(\text{GBH})_3^{3+}$ and $\text{Cr}(\text{GBH})_3\text{X}^{2+}$ have been evaluated from limiting conductance data using Stokes law and from the association constants of the ion-pairs using Bjerrum relationship.

OUTER-SPHERE complexations have been comparatively less studied in the case of transition metal complex salts, and more so in chromium(III) complexes. Adamson and Wilkins¹ suggested in 1954 that hexaaquochromium(III) formed ion-pair with SCN^- , which was later studied spectrophotometrically by Postmus and King², who determined the association constant of $\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6\text{SCN}^{2+}$ to be 7. The association constant of $\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6\text{Cl}^{2+}$ was earlier determined by Connick and Tsao³ to be 13. Mironov and coworkers⁴ studied the equilibria between $\text{Cr}(\text{en})_3^{3+}$ and $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$, SO_3^{2-} , SeO_3^{2-} and CO_3^{2-} , using solubility and calorimetric methods and calculated the stepwise changes in enthalpy and entropy during ion-pair formation.

One of the important reasons for chromium(III) complexes being less studied appears to be their tendency to hydrolyse much faster than more studied metal complexes in aqueous solutions during experimental manipulations. Recently, one of us has reported⁵ that the cationic tris-chelate, $\text{Cr}(\text{GBH})_3^{3+}$, formed by 2-guanidinobenzimidazole (GBH), $\text{C}_6\text{H}_4 - \text{NH} - \text{C}(=\text{N}) - \text{NH} - \text{C}(=\text{NH}) - \text{NH}_2$, with

chromium(III) is quite stable in aqueous solutions. The chloride, bromide, and nitrate of this cationic complex, being highly soluble 3 : 1 electrolytes, have been chosen for the present conductometric investigations in aqueous solutions. This appears to be the first report on a conductometric study of outer-sphere complexation in chromium(III) complex salts.

Association Constants of Ion-pairs :

The ionic equilibrium between the trivalent complex cation, $\text{Cr}(\text{GBH})_3^{3+}$, and the monovalent

anion, X^- (Cl^- , Br^- , or NO_3^-), may be expressed as follows :

The dissociation constant, K, of the ion-pair is given by

$$K = \frac{[\text{Cr}(\text{GBH})_3^{3+}][\text{X}^-]}{[\text{Cr}(\text{GBH})_3\text{X}^{2+}]} = \frac{(2+\alpha)mf_1f_2}{(1-\alpha)f_3} \quad \dots (1)$$

where α represents the degree of dissociation of the ion-pair and f_1 , f_2 and f_3 are the activity coefficients of X^- , $\text{Cr}(\text{GBH})_3\text{X}^{2+}$, and $\text{Cr}(\text{GBH})_3^{3+}$, respectively. The activity coefficient, f_i , of an ionic species in very dilute solutions has been calculated from the Debye-Hückel limiting law⁶

$$\log f_i = -Az_i^2I^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad \dots (2)$$

where $A = 1.823 \times 10^6 / (\text{DT})^{\frac{3}{2}}$ (0.509 at 25°, 0.519 at 35° and 0.529 at 45° for water as solvent), z_i is the charge of the ionic species and I is the ionic strength, given by $(1+\alpha)C$, C being the equivalent concentration.

The degree of dissociation, α , has been evaluated from conductance measurements. The Debye-Hückel-Onsager limiting conductivity equation(3)⁷ may be used for extrapolating the limiting conductivity of the electrolyte :

$$\Lambda_{\text{ext}} = \Lambda^\circ - \left[\frac{2 \cdot 801 \times 10^6 |z_1 z_2| q \Lambda^\circ}{(\epsilon T)^{3/2} (1 + \sqrt{q})} + \frac{41 \cdot 25 (|z_1| + |z_2|)}{\eta(\epsilon T)^{\frac{1}{2}}} \right] I^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad \dots (3)$$

$$\text{where } q = \frac{|z_1 z_2|}{|z_1| + |z_2|} \cdot \frac{\lambda_1^\circ + \lambda_2^\circ}{|z_2| \lambda_1^\circ + |z_1| \lambda_2^\circ}$$

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Incorporating the values of dielectric constant ϵ and viscosity coefficient η at a given temperature T in the constant terms in Equation (3)

$$\Lambda_{\text{expt}} = \Lambda^\circ - \left[\frac{A |z_1 z_2| q \Lambda^\circ}{1 + \sqrt{q}} + B (|z_1| + |z_2|) \right] I^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad \dots (4)$$

where, $A=0.7852$ (25°), 0.8006 (35°) and 0.8178 (45°) and $B=30.32$ (25°), 37.76 (35°) and 45.86 (45°). As I is directly proportional to C , a graphical determination of Λ° is possible by using the above equation in the general form :

$$\Lambda_{\text{expt}} = \Lambda^\circ - bC^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

The value of $\Lambda^\circ_{\text{approx}}$ is obtained by extrapolating the plot of Λ_{expt} vs $C^{\frac{1}{2}}$ (Fig. 1) and then more accurate values, $\Lambda^\circ_{\text{onsager}}$, are obtained from the plot of $(\Lambda_{\text{expt}} + bC^{\frac{1}{2}})$ against C (Fig. 2). The

Fig. 1. Graphical evaluation of $\Lambda^\circ_{\text{approx}}$ at 25°C †

Fig. 2. Graphical evaluation of $\Lambda^\circ_{\text{onsager}}$ at 25°C †

† For clarity, the curves for results at 35° and 45° are not reproduced here.

limiting conductivities of the cation, $\text{Cr}(\text{GBH})_3^{3+}$, are calculated by deducting the mobilities of the respective anions⁹. The limiting conductivity of the bivalent ion-pair, $\text{Cr}(\text{GBH})_3 X^{2+}$ may be taken as two-thirds⁹ of that of the trivalent ion, $\text{Cr}(\text{GBH})_3^{3+}$, and thus the limiting conductivity of the 2:1 valent salt $\text{Cr}(\text{GBH})_3 X^{2+} \cdot 2X^-$ may be calculated. Now, the equations for $\Lambda_{s:1}$ and $\Lambda_{2:1}$ for the four salts are set up in the general form $\Lambda_{\text{expt}} = \Lambda^\circ_{\text{ons}} - bI^{\frac{1}{2}}$ for which the values of $\Lambda^\circ_{\text{ons}}$ and b at different temperatures are presented in Table 1.

TABLE 1—THE VALUES OF $\Lambda^\circ_{\text{ons}}$ AND b FOR THE EQUATION $\Lambda_{\text{expt}} = \Lambda^\circ_{\text{ons}} - bI^{\frac{1}{2}}$

Salt	Valence type	$\Lambda^\circ_{\text{ons}}$			b		
		25°	35°	45°	25°	35°	45°
Chloride	3 : 1	117.40	189.20	156.00	179.10	220.12	261.72
	2 : 1	103.72	123.54	140.21	129.69	159.95	190.93
Bromide	3 : 1	120.40	140.60	160.00	180.37	220.65	262.58
	2 : 1	106.31	125.08	143.56	130.79	160.42	192.37
Nitrate	3 : 1	115.00	182.00	151.30	178.76	217.55	258.80
	2 : 1	100.49	116.49	134.54	128.87	157.62	189.38

If the total molar concentration of $[\text{Cr}(\text{GBH})_3]_s X_s$ be m , the specific conductivity of the solution is given by¹⁰ :

$$10^8 k = 3\alpha m \lambda_{\text{Or}(\text{GBH})_3^{3+}} + 2(1-\alpha)m \lambda_{\text{Or}(\text{GBH})_3^{2+}} + (2+\alpha)m \lambda_{X^-} \\ = 3\alpha m \Lambda_{s:1} + 2(1-\alpha)m \Lambda_{2:1}$$

$$\text{Or, } \Lambda_{\text{expt}} = \alpha \Lambda_{s:1} + \frac{2}{3}(1-\alpha)\Lambda_{2:1} \quad \dots (5)$$

This equation (5) assumes the following general form :

$$\alpha = \frac{\Lambda_{\text{expt}} + EI^{\frac{1}{2}} - F}{G - HI^{\frac{1}{2}}} \quad \dots (6)$$

where E, F, G and H are constants depending on the equations for $\Lambda_{s:1}$ and $\Lambda_{2:1}$. Using the above equation in conjunction with the following :

$$I^{\frac{1}{2}} = [(1+\alpha)C]^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad \dots (7)$$

the value of α is calculated by titration. Starting with the value of α as 1 in Equation (7), and substituting the corresponding value of $I^{\frac{1}{2}}$ in equation (6), a truer value of α is obtained, which is again fed into Equation (7) and in this way the cycle is repeated till the constant value of α is obtained. The values of α thus calculated for different readings are presented in Table 2. The corresponding values

of $I^{\frac{1}{2}}$ are then used in Equation (2) to calculate the activity coefficients of the ionic species, which in turn lead to the evaluation of dissociation constants of the ion-pairs through Equation (1).

(Table 2 Cont.)

TABLE 2—ASSOCIATION CONSTANTS OF Cr(GBH)₃X³⁺

X ⁻ =Cl ⁻ (25°±0.05°C)						X ⁻ =Br ⁻ (45°±0.05°C)										
10°C	10°C [‡]	Λ _{expt}	Λ _{expt} +bC [‡]	κ	¹⁰ K (mole l ⁻¹)	10°C	10°C [‡]	Λ _{expt}	Λ _{expt} +bC [‡]	κ	¹⁰ K (mole l ⁻¹)	K _A (1.mole ⁻¹)	¹⁰ K (mole l ⁻¹)	K _A (1.mole ⁻¹)		
20.02	4.474	103.102	111.070	0.9263	15.90	16.56	4.070	143.288	153.975	0.9697	34.53	60.8	34.53	30.0		
16.66	4.081	104.109	111.378	0.9280	14.06	14.49	3.535	145.240	154.522	0.9699	27.71		27.71			
14.24	3.775	105.349	112.072	0.9404	15.22	11.13	3.336	146.204	154.964	0.9743	29.68		29.68			
12.56	3.540	106.079	112.333	0.9446	14.84	10.08	3.175	145.084	155.420	0.9796	34.66		34.66			
11.12	3.335	106.888	112.827	0.9517	15.40	8.34	2.888	148.410	155.943	0.9841	38.02		38.02			
10.05	3.170	107.467	113.113	0.9559	15.73	7.12	2.668	149.005	156.011	0.9808	27.45		27.45			
8.33	2.886	108.272	113.413	0.9586	14.99	6.18	2.486	149.880	156.407	0.9847	30.62		30.62			
7.14	2.672	108.876	113.645	0.9604	14.24	5.54	2.354	150.529	156.709	0.9873	35.63		35.63			
6.25	2.500	109.922	114.374	0.9747	18.63	5.04	2.245	151.110	157.004	0.9905	41.54		41.54			
5.55	2.356	110.477	114.677	0.9792	20.59	Average: 33.32 ± 4.81										
5.02	2.240	110.825	114.898	0.9806	20.22											
4.16	2.039	111.389	115.021	0.9820	18.43											
Average: 16.46 ± 2.36						X ⁻ =NO ₃ ⁻ (25°±0.05°C)										
						16.60	4.074	103.048	110.930	0.9588	25.51		41.8		25.51	31.7
						14.20	3.768	104.098	110.833	0.9662	27.64	27.64				
						12.50	3.535	104.976	111.295	0.9736	32.21	32.21				
						11.10	3.331	105.702	111.656	-0.9789	36.76	36.76				
						10.00	3.162	106.096	111.718	0.9783	32.67	32.67				
						8.30	2.880	106.870	112.018	0.9800	30.34	30.34				
						7.10	2.664	107.608	112.370	0.9847	34.84	34.84				
						6.20	2.489	108.106	112.555	0.9861	34.18	34.18				
						5.50	2.345	108.542	112.734	0.9878	35.13	35.13				
						5.00	2.236	108.845	112.833	0.9885	34.21	34.21				
						4.10	2.024	109.267	112.985	0.9861	23.71	23.71				
						Average: 31.56 ± 4.26										
						X ⁻ =NO ₃ ⁻ (35°±0.05°C)										
						16.60	4.074	118.217	127.156	0.9712	36.79	36.1		36.79	29.2	
						14.20	3.763	119.097	127.272	0.9704	31.55		31.55			
						12.50	3.535	119.966	127.576	0.9728	31.03		31.03			
						11.10	3.331	120.809	128.037	0.9790	36.12		36.12			
						8.30	2.880	122.278	128.526	0.9813	32.36		32.36			
						7.1	2.664	123.019	128.799	0.9831	31.38		31.38			
						6.2	2.489	123.901	129.301	0.9883	40.56		40.56			
						Average: 34.26 ± 3.68										
						X ⁻ =NO ₃ ⁻ (45°±0.05°C)										
						16.60	4.074	135.189	145.733	0.9767	45.39		36.1	45.39		24.4
						14.20	3.768	136.295	146.047	0.9782	42.91			42.91		
						12.50	3.535	137.124	146.273	0.9780	38.32			38.32		
						11.10	3.331	137.905	146.525	0.9789	36.28			36.28		
						10.00	3.162	138.855	147.038	0.9853	48.17			48.17		
						8.30	2.880	139.764	147.217	0.9833	36.11	36.11				
						7.10	2.664	140.740	147.635	0.9869	40.45	40.45				
						6.20	2.489	141.456	147.897	0.9884	40.69	40.69				
						Average: 41.04 ± 4.28										
						X ⁻ =Cl ⁻ (35°±0.05°C)										
20.02	4.474	123.091	133.920	0.9524	25.18							36.1		25.18	29.2	
16.66	4.081	124.567	133.534	0.9537	25.33									25.33		
14.24	3.775	125.667	133.960	0.9624	24.63									24.63		
12.56	3.540	126.423	134.200	0.9635	22.95									22.95		
11.12	3.335	127.148	134.475	0.9655	23.00								23.00			
10.05	3.170	127.843	134.807	0.9720	25.12								25.12			
8.33	2.886	128.833	135.174	0.9720	21.42								21.42			
7.14	2.672	129.674	135.544	0.9757	21.26								21.26			
6.25	2.500	130.478	135.970	0.9812	25.19								25.19			
5.55	2.356	131.041	136.222	0.9835	25.93								25.93			
						Average: 23.90 ± 1.80										
						X ⁻ =Cl ⁻ (45°±0.05°C)										
20.02	4.474	137.544	149.253	0.9620	31.63								45.6	31.63		29.2
16.66	4.081	139.044	149.726	0.9638	28.83									28.83		
14.24	3.775	140.310	150.144	0.9667	27.92							27.92				
12.56	3.540	141.302	150.737	0.9699	27.85							27.85				
11.12	3.335	142.010	150.737	0.9690	24.42							24.42				
10.05	3.170	142.742	151.039	0.9716	24.58							24.58				
7.14	2.672	145.065	152.158	0.9810	27.81							27.81				
6.25	2.500	145.724	152.267	0.9816	25.16							25.16				
5.55	2.356	146.411	152.693	0.9844	27.32							27.32				
5.02	2.240	147.001	152.987	0.9874	31.03							31.03				
						Average: 27.66 ± 2.48										
						X ⁻ =Br ⁻ (25°±0.05°C)										
16.56	4.070	107.575	114.916	0.9415	17.53							45.6		17.53	29.2	
12.49	3.535	109.742	116.118	0.9617	21.85									21.85		
11.13	3.336	110.324	116.341	0.9638	21.06								21.06			
10.68	3.175	111.080	116.807	0.9720	25.31								25.31			
8.34	2.888	111.906	117.115	0.9745	23.73								23.73			
7.12	2.668	112.471	117.283	0.9749	21.04								21.04			
6.18	2.486	113.063	117.646	0.9779	21.18								21.18			
5.54	2.354	113.515	117.759	0.9806	22.04								22.04			
5.04	2.245	113.907	117.956	0.9832	23.56								23.56			
						Average: 21.92 ± 2.20										
						X ⁻ =Br ⁻ (35°±0.05°C)										
16.56	4.070	127.000	135.975	0.9697	34.83								35.0	34.83		24.4
12.49	3.535	128.540	136.335	0.9678	26.02									26.02		
11.13	3.336	129.482	136.838	0.9746	30.26									30.26		
10.08	3.175	130.232	137.233	0.9797	35.08							35.08				
8.34	2.888	131.000	137.369	0.9775	26.88							26.88				
7.12	2.668	131.804	137.687	0.9800	26.43							26.43				
6.18	2.486	132.428	137.910	0.9813	25.08							25.08				
5.54	2.354	132.981	138.172	0.9841	26.89							26.89				
5.04	2.245	133.380	138.300	0.9847	25.72							25.72				
						Average: 28.58 ± 3.89										

The degrees of dissociation of the ion-pairs under investigation and their association constants have been found to be of the same order as determined earlier for certain cobalt(III) complex salts by similar methods¹⁰⁻¹³. Association constant of Cl⁻ with Cr(GBH)₃³⁺ ranges from 60.8 to 36.2 between 25° and 45°, whereas that with Co(NH₃)₆³⁺ was reported¹³ to be 74 at 25°, with Co(en)₃³⁺ to be¹⁰ 52 at 25° and with Co(BigH)₃³⁺ to be^{11,12} 55 at 25° and 62 at 35°. Bromide ion association of Cr(GBH)₃³⁺ (K_A=45.6-30.1 at 25°-45°) is stronger than that of Co(en)₃³⁺ (K_A=21 at 25°)¹³ and Co(BigH)₃³⁺ (K_A=34-37 at 25°-35°), but similar to that of Co(NH₃)₆³⁺ (K_A=46 at 25°)¹³. No work is available on nitrate ion association of these cations

and thus the present investigation of such an association appears to be unique. The association constants for NO_3^- with $\text{Cr}(\text{GBH})_3^{3+}$ vary from 31.7 at 25° to 24.4 at 45°. Thus the previous impression that chromium(III) complex cations formed much weaker associates with anions as compared to the cobalt(III) complex cations appears to have been based on studies in small number of systems and hence requires revision in the light of present investigation.

Thermodynamic Parameters :

The changes in free energy (ΔG°) have been calculated from the equilibrium constants of the ion-pairs using the formula $\Delta G^\circ = -RT \cdot \ln K_A$ and the values (Table 3) are in the vicinity -2-2.5

TABLE 3—THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS

Salt	T	K_A (1.mole ⁻¹)	$-\Delta G^\circ$ (cal mole ⁻¹)	ΔH° (cal mole ⁻¹)	ΔS° (cal mole ⁻¹ deg ⁻¹)
Chloride	298	60.8	2494	5336	26.07
	308	41.8	2285		21.74
	318	36.2	2268		23.91
Bromide	298	45.6	2262	4295	22.00
	308	35.0	2176		21.01
	318	30.1	2152		20.27
Nitrate	298	31.7	2047	3268	17.84
	308	29.2	2063		17.31
	318	24.4	2019		16.63

kcal mole⁻¹. The values of $\log K_A$ when plotted against $\frac{1}{T}$ gave a straight line in every case (Fig. 3), the slope of which was equated to $-\Delta H^\circ/4.576$ to evaluate ΔH° (5336 cal mole⁻¹ for chloride, 4295 cal mole⁻¹ for bromide and 3268 cal mole⁻¹ for nitrate). The entropy change (ΔS°) has been calculated from the relation $T\Delta S^\circ = \Delta H^\circ - \Delta G^\circ$ which is found to decrease slightly with increasing temperature.

Fig. 3. The plot of $\log K_A$ vs. $1/T$, from the slope of which is calculated the enthalpy change.

A positive entropy change has often been explained¹⁴ on the assumption that the 'iceberg' structure around the cation is broken when ion-association takes place, leading to an increase in the

degree of disorderness. It has been suggested by Dey and Dutta¹⁵ that with increase in temperature, such effects are responsible for increase in association constant values and consequently in entropy changes in the tris(biguanidinium)cobalt(III) salts. But the reverse observation in the present case probably suggests that the breaking of the solvent structure around the complex cation is not the predominant phenomenon in our system. The system under investigation may be treated to have obeyed the simple law of increasing dissociation at higher temperature³.

Sizes of the Ionic Species :

The limiting conductivity of $\text{Cr}(\text{GBH})_3^{3+}$ directly gives the ionic radius 'a' through Stokes law¹⁶ :

$$a = 9.16 \times 10^{-7} z_1 / \lambda_1 \quad \dots (8)$$

The radii of ion-pairs calculated by the addition of Stokes radii of the anions at 25° (λ ; Cl^- : 76.35, Br^- : 78.14, NO_3^- : 71.46)¹⁶ have been shown in Table 4.

TABLE 4—IONIC SIZES AT 25°C

Cation/Anion		Ion-Pair	
Species	Stokes Radius (Å)	Species	Radius (Å)
			Stokes Bjerrum
$\text{Cr}(\text{GBH})_3^{3+}$	6.44	$\text{Cr}(\text{GBH})_3\text{Cl}^{2+}$	7.64 4.04
Cl^-	1.20*	$\text{Cr}(\text{GBH})_3\text{Br}^{2+}$	7.61 4.91
Br^-	1.17*	$\text{Cr}(\text{GBH})_3\text{NO}_3^{2+}$	7.72 6.29
NO_3^-	1.28*		

* Ref. 16.

The complex cation $\text{Cr}(\text{GBH})_3^{3+}$ appears to be much larger (6.44 Å) than $\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6^{3+}$ (2.77 Å)¹⁰, $\text{Co}(\text{en})_3^{3+}$ (3.68 Å)¹⁰, $\text{Co}(\text{pn})_3^{3+}$ (4.23 Å)¹⁰ and $\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_3^{3+}$ (4.03 Å)¹², which is in accordance with the size of the ligand.

The sizes of the ion-pairs have also been obtained from their association constants by using the Bjerrum relationship¹⁷ :

$$K_A = \frac{4\pi N}{1000} \left(\frac{z_1 z_2 b^2}{\epsilon k T} \right)^3 Q(b) \quad \dots (9)$$

$$Q(b) = \int_a^b x^{-4} b^2 dx$$

$$x = z_1 z_2 b / \epsilon k T$$

$$b = z_1 z_2 b^2 / a \epsilon k T$$

The mathematical complications have been simplified by directly obtaining the value of b from a plot of $Q(b)$ vs b as suggested by Monk¹⁷, and then evaluating a, the closest distance of approach of the ionic species. The Stokes radii of the ion-pairs have been compared with those of Bjerrum distances in Table 4, but unfortunately, the two

results do not agree. Such deviations have also been observed by Jenkins and Monk¹⁰ for Cl^- and SO_4^{2-} ion associates with $\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6^{2+}$, $\text{Co}(\text{en})_3^{2+}$ and $\text{Co}(\text{pn})_3^{2+}$ and by De and Dutta¹² for Cl^- , Br^- , I^- and SO_4^{2-} ion associates with $\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_3^{2+}$.

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